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GREEN RECOVERY OF BIOACTIVE EXTRACTS FROM PLANTS AND ALGAE FOR SUSTAINABLE FISHFEED APPLICATIONS

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Introduction: Edible plants, herbs, and algae are rich sources of natural compounds with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. Within the Horizon Europe FEEDACTIV project (Grant No. 101086261), we investigated their potential for use in fishfeed, focusing on sustainable recovery through green extraction technologies.

Aims: To identify and recover bioactive ingredients from selected species using eco-friendly techniques and to evaluate their antimicrobial and antioxidant capacity for feed supplement development.

Materials and Methods: Agro-industrial by-products such as olive leaves, lemon and orange peels, and blueberry leaves, along with herbs (thyme, garlic, rosemary, eucalyptus) and algae (Spirulina, Chlorella, Ulva), were selected based on literature and bioactivity. Extraction was carried out using ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), high-pressure extraction, Soxhlet, and combined ultrasound-microwave assisted extraction. The extracts were analyzed for total phenolics, flavonoids, antioxidant activity, and chemical composition (HPLC, GC-MS).

Results: Citrus peel and olive leaf extracts showed high phenolic content (up to 93 mg GAE/g), especially using UAE and PLE with water or ethyl acetate. Essential oils of garlic and thyme exhibited superior antimicrobial activity, outperforming gentamicin and fluconazole in vitro. Microalgal extracts were rich in proteins and phycocyanin, with antioxidant activity exceeding 300 µg Trolox/g dry weight. GC-MS profiles revealed compound-specific potency (e.g., thymol, carvacrol, eucalyptol).

Conclusion: Selected herbs, plants, and algae demonstrate high bioactivity when recovered via green extraction. These results support their integration as natural, sustainable additives in aquafeed to enhance health, immunity, and environmental performance.

Keywords: algae, bioactive compounds, essential oils, fishfeed, green extraction.

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